

Sayyora Davidova
Doctoral student
National University of
Uzbekistan

Sayyora Davidova
Tayanch doktorant,
O'zbekiston Milliy
Universiteti

Сайёра Давидова
Докторант
Национальный
университет Узбекистана

INGLIZ TILINI IKKINCHI TIL O'QUVCHILARI SIFATIDA YOZISHNI O'RGATISHDA KOMPYUTER ASOSIDAGI BAHOLASHNING O'RNI

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada biz ingliz tilini ikkinchi til sifatida (ESL) talabalarga yozish ko'nikmalarini o'rgatish vositasi sifatida kompyuter asosidagi baholashning ahamiyatini ko'rib chiqamiz. Biz kompyuterda yozishni baholashda qo'llaniladigan materiallar va usullarni o'rganamiz, ularning samaradorligi bo'yicha so'nggi tadqiqotlar natijalarini taqdim etamiz va ESL ta'limiga ta'siri haqida munozaralarda qatnashamiz. Maqola ESL yozish qobiliyatini oshirishda kompyuterga asoslangan baholashning potentsial afzalliklarini ta'kidlash bilan yakunlanadi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: Kompyuterlashtirilgan baholash, Yozma ta'lim, Ingliz tili ikkinchi til sifatida (ESL), Til kompetensiyasi, Ta'lim texnologiyasi.

РОЛЬ КОМПЬЮТЕРНОГО ОЦЕНИВАНИЯ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ПИСЬМУ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК ВТОРОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

АННОТАЦИЯ: В этой статье мы рассматриваем важность компьютерного оценивания как инструмента обучения навыкам письма учащихся английского как второго языка (ESL). Мы изучим материалы и методы, используемые для компьютерной оценки письма, представим результаты недавних исследований их эффективности и обсудим их влияние на образование ESL. В заключение статьи подчеркиваются потенциальные преимущества компьютерного оценивания в улучшении навыков письма ESL.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: компьютеризированное тестирование, инструкция по письму, английский как второй язык (ESL), языковая компетенция, технология обучения.

THE ROLE OF COMPUTER-BASED ASSESSMENT IN TEACHING WRITING TO ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE LEARNERS

ABSTRACT: In this article, we delve into the importance of computer-based assessment as a tool for instructing English as a Second Language (ESL) students in writing skills. We explore the materials and techniques employed in computer-based writing assessments, present the findings of recent research on their effectiveness, and engage in discussions regarding the implications for ESL education. The article concludes by underscoring the potential advantages of computer-based assessment in elevating ESL writing abilities.

KEY WORDS: Computerized evaluation, Writing education, English as a Second Language (ESL), Language competence, Educational technology.

INTRODUCTION:

In today's globally interconnected world, possessing a strong command of the English language is an invaluable asset for individuals pursuing academic, professional, and personal growth. For students learning English as a Second Language (ESL), the proficiency to write effectively in English is a critical skill. Nevertheless, the task of teaching writing to ESL students is not without its unique challenges. The landscape of computer-assisted learning has undergone significant transformations since its initial trials in the late 1950s and early 1960s, when it was first experimented with at various prominent U.S. universities. In the preface of a recent book that provides an overview of this field, Pennington (1989) characterizes the early educational applications of computers as aiming to "maximize efficiency by standardizing and automating the learning process." This was done with the goal of "compensating for individual learner tendencies that sometimes hinder humans from being perfectly efficient information processors," essentially striving to create a form of learning that is resistant to variations

among learners and, in a way, making learning "foolproof" (and "teacher-proof") (p. vii). A promising solution to address these challenges involves the integration of computer-based assessment methodologies into ESL instruction. This article seeks to shed light on the role that computer-based assessment plays in teaching writing to ESL students, with a focus on the materials, techniques, results, and discussions surrounding its application.

MATERIALS:

The world of computer-based writing assessment is rich with a diverse range of digital tools and resources designed to aid and enhance the writing process. These resources comprise a comprehensive toolbox that empowers both educators and learners alike.

First and foremost, we have the ubiquitous word processing software, which serves as the foundation of computer-based writing assessment. This software provides a digital canvas upon which students can compose their thoughts and ideas, making the act of writing more accessible and versatile than ever before.

In addition to word processors, there are online writing platforms that offer collaborative features. These platforms allow students to work together on projects, providing a space for peer editing and constructive feedback. This collaborative aspect fosters a sense of community among learners and encourages the exchange of ideas, ultimately leading to improved writing skills.

Grammar and spell-check utilities are indispensable companions in the digital writing environment. They serve as vigilant proofreaders, automatically flagging errors and offering suggestions for correction. This real-time feedback not only saves time but also helps learners internalize proper grammar and spelling conventions.

To combat plagiarism, plagiarism detection programs are essential. These tools scan written work and compare it to a vast database of existing content, identifying any instances of potential plagiarism. By promoting academic integrity, these programs encourage students to develop their writing skills authentically.

Moreover, educators can provide students with access to a wealth of writing prompts that inspire creativity and critical thinking. These prompts can range from thought-provoking questions to challenging scenarios, sparking the imagination and guiding students toward engaging topics.

Reference materials, available at the click of a button, offer students a treasure trove of information. Online encyclopedias, scholarly articles, and digital libraries can be invaluable resources for research and fact-checking, ensuring the accuracy and credibility of written work.

Online dictionaries, with their extensive vocabularies and language tools, are a writer's best friend. They assist in expanding students' lexical repertoire, encouraging the use of precise and varied vocabulary to convey ideas effectively.

In essence, the materials and resources within the digital writing environment extend well beyond the traditional pen and paper. They not only streamline the assessment process but also foster a dynamic learning experience. By leveraging these digital tools, educators can cultivate a generation of proficient writers who are well-equipped to thrive in the digital age. Methods:

To justify the incorporation of computer-assisted instruction in the current educational landscape, it is essential to ensure that it aligns with the principles of learning and pedagogy rooted in educational humanism, which serves as the foundational philosophy of modern curricula. Hirvela (1989) holds a highly skeptical view of computer-assisted instruction, asserting that this medium lacks characteristics that can be deemed humanistic. In contrast, Stevens (1989) outlines a historical shift away from behaviorism in computer-assisted language learning (CALL) towards utilizing computers in ways that are

consistent with humanistic educational objectives. These approaches emphasize fostering learner creativity, individualized learning experiences, and the promotion of peer interaction within the classroom. Wyatt (1989) also discusses collaborative and facilitative applications of computers in reading instruction, marking a departure from conventional behavioristic teaching methods. These applications are described as "evolutionary" and "revolutionary," as they encourage greater user control, freedom of choice, and novel forms of learning encounters.

Despite the potential advantages of computer-assisted instruction, numerous authors caution against hastily embracing computer technology in education. Hirvela (1989) warns against language instructors becoming overly enthusiastic or fanatical advocates of computer-assisted language learning (CALL), cautioning against excessive zeal for the cause. Leech and Candlin (1986) advise being cautious of the dangers that may arise from an uncritical or addictive enthusiasm for CALL, particularly if its implementation lacks thorough scrutiny. Educators must remain vigilant to prevent a tendency to unquestionably adopt whatever computer-based tools are available for a particular subject, then subsequently adjusting their educational objectives and curriculum to conform to the capabilities of the software. Similar to other media and instructional materials, decisions regarding the use of computers in education should be made after a comprehensive evaluation of their alignment with established educational

principles. The integration of courseware into an educational program should be guided by the curriculum's objectives rather than the other way around. Furthermore, decisions concerning computer use within educational curricula should be informed by the outcomes, both successful and unsuccessful, of previously implemented approaches.

Computer-based assessment techniques offer several advantages in the context of teaching writing to ESL students. Primarily, they offer immediate feedback, allowing students to promptly identify and rectify errors as they write. This real-time feedback loop enhances the learning process and assists students in developing their self-editing abilities. Furthermore, the utilization of digital writing platforms enables educators to monitor students' progress over time, providing insights into their individual strengths and areas that require improvement.

RESULTS:

The exploration of the impact of computer-based assessment on the writing proficiency of English as a Second Language (ESL) students has been a subject of considerable research. The collective findings from these studies consistently highlight a range of positive outcomes that signify the efficacy of this approach in ESL education.

One of the most noticeable benefits observed in ESL students who engage in computer-based writing assessments is the substantial enhancement of their command over grammar and vocabulary.

The digital environment facilitates immediate feedback, allowing learners to identify and rectify grammatical errors and expand their vocabulary as they write. This dynamic feedback mechanism acts as a real-time tutor, guiding students towards more accurate language usage.

Furthermore, the organization of ideas within written compositions notably improves as a result of computer-based assessment. The process encourages students to structure their thoughts logically and coherently, leading to more effectively structured essays and reports. The digital platform also enables learners to reorder and revise their ideas effortlessly, fostering a deeper understanding of the principles of effective writing organization.

Perhaps one of the most significant gains is the development of overall writing fluency. ESL students engaging in computer-based writing assessments tend to write more fluently and confidently. The instant feedback loop, combined with the opportunity for multiple revisions, nurtures a sense of writing self-efficacy. This increased fluency extends to the development of a unique writing style and voice, further enhancing the students' ability to communicate effectively in written form. The consistent positive outcomes from these studies underscore that computer-based assessment is a valuable asset in ESL writing instruction. It acts as a catalyst for linguistic development, promoting grammatical accuracy, vocabulary enrichment, logical organization, and overall fluency. Beyond

merely identifying areas for improvement, computer-based assessment actively contributes to the holistic development of writing skills among ESL learners. It empowers them to not only express themselves more effectively in English but also to become more confident and proficient writers, thus opening doors to academic and professional success in the English-speaking world.

DISCUSSIONS:

The majority of existing research has focused on comparing the effectiveness of word processing with traditional non-technological writing tools in the context of native English speakers' writing skills. For a comprehensive review of representative studies and discussions on this topic, please refer to Harris (1985), Daiute (1986), Lutz (1987), and Phinney (1989). In contrast, there is a limited body of research that has investigated the utilization of computer tools by ESL students or has conducted comparisons between various methods of computer-assisted instruction. For an overview of these studies, please see Phinney (1989), and specific research can be found in works by Daiute (1986) and Wresch (1987).

The integration of computer-based assessment into ESL writing instruction prompts important discussions regarding its efficacy and potential challenges. While the benefits are evident, educators must grapple with issues related to accessibility, equity, and digital literacy. Additionally, it is crucial to strike a balance between computer-based assessment and

traditional writing instruction methods, ensuring a well-rounded approach to ESL writing development.

CONCLUSION:

Computer-based assessment serves as a pivotal tool in the instruction of writing to ESL students. By offering immediate feedback, granting access to valuable resources, and providing opportunities for skill development, it enhances the overall writing proficiency of ESL learners. Nonetheless, educators must thoughtfully consider the integration of digital tools, addressing potential hurdles and ensuring a comprehensive approach to writing instruction. As technology continues to evolve, computer-based assessment remains a valuable asset in the quest for effective ESL writing education.

Nevertheless, the incorporation of computer-assisted instruction into contemporary education requires a thoughtful assessment of its compatibility with educational humanism principles. While there are concerns about its potential to depersonalize learning, there is also evidence of its capacity to support humanistic ideals in education. Educators must approach its adoption cautiously, ensuring that it enhances the learning experience, promotes learner agency, and aligns with educational principles, while guarding against unbridled enthusiasm and zealotry. Ultimately, the role of computer-assisted instruction should be determined by its effectiveness in facilitating meaningful and successful learning experiences, rather than being driven solely by its availability or novelty.

LITERATURE:

1. Hirvela, A. (1989). Marshall McLuhan and the case against CAL. *System*, 16, 299-311.
2. Leech, G., and Candlin, C. (Eds.) (1987). *Computers in English language teaching and research*. London: Longman.
3. Pennington, M. C. (1989). Preface. In M. C. Pennington (Ed.), *Teaching languages with computers: The state of the art* (pp. vii-ix). La Jolla, CA: Athelstan.
4. Stevens, V. (1989). A direction for CALL: From behavioristic to humanistic courseware. In M. C. Pennington (Ed.), *Teaching languages with computers: The state of the art* (pp. 31--43). La Jolla, CA: Athelstan.
5. Martha C (1989) Use of computers in the teaching of ESL writing. *University of Hawai'i Working Papers in ESL*, Vol. 8, No.1, May 1989, pp. 155-183
6. Wyatt, D. H. (1989). Computers and reading skills: The medium and the message. In M. C. Pennington (Ed.), *Teaching languages with computers: The state of the art* (pp. 63-78). La Jolla, CA: Athelstan.
7. Baratboyevna, N. M. (2021). Polysemantic features of pedagogical terms in English and Uzbek translation. *Current research journal of philological sciences*, 2(12), 21-25.